

STUDIES ON YEAST NUCLEIC ACID. PART II. INTERACTION WITH BASES AND ACIDS

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Interaction of the yeast nucleic acid with bases and acid has been studied by potentiometric and conductometric titrations. Results of potentiometric titration with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, KOH , NaOH and NH_4OH show that this nucleic acid has no fixed total acidity which is found to vary slightly in the order: $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{KOH} > \text{NaOH} > \text{NH}_4\text{OH}$. Conductometric titration curves with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ present peculiar shapes. Nucleic acid interacts with HCl in the same way as phosphoric acid.

From variation of H-ion activity, specific conductance and cataphoretic velocity with concentration of the yeast nucleic acid solution as communicated in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 65) it was concluded that there might be some type of aggregate formation on the part of the anions (nucleiate ions) occurring in this system. It has also been observed that there is no definite critical concentration for these systems because different physical properties, when plotted against concentration of the solution, show breaks in different concentration regions, widely differing from one another. Thus, the nature of variation of the physical properties together with the absence of any definite critical concentration (*cf.* Hartley, *Kolloid Z.*, 1939, **88**, 22) has led to the conclusion that most probably in these systems the process of aggregate formation is not sudden but progressive, proceeding at all concentrations and different physical and electrochemical properties, when plotted against concentration, show breaks depending on the nature of the property and the degree of aggregation.

The present investigations were undertaken with a view to examining this point further from evidences obtained from interaction of the yeast nucleic acid solution with different bases and acids.

Both potentiometric and conductometric methods have been employed. Five different bases viz., NH_4OH , NaOH , KOH , $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ have been studied in this connection. The acid used was HCl only.

EXPERIMENTAL

The methods of purification of the acid and preparation of the sol were the same as reported in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The acid content of these solutions was approximately the same viz., 2 g. per litre of the solution.

Potentiometric and conductometric measurements were carried out at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in an electrically regulated thermostat. Usual precautions, e.g., frequent replatinisation of the platinised platinum electrodes, were taken for p_B measurements (*vide* J. N. Mukherjee, and co-workers, *J. Indian Agric. Sci.*, 1936, **6**, 571). Quinhydrone electrode has not been used in these titrations as this is known to yield inaccurate results beyond p_B 7.6.

Interaction with Bases

(i) *Potentiometric Titration.*—Reproducibility of the potentiometric measurements was first checked by titrating the same solution on two different occasions by the same base, e.g., NaOH . The result is presented in Fig. 1. The two titration curves run

almost coincident, so much so, that it is difficult to distinguish them as two distinct curves for the greater part of their course.

From titration curves with different bases, given in Fig. 2, it is evident that with all the bases excepting NH_4OH the titrations could be pushed to a high p_n (above 10). With NH_4OH , the titration curve becomes flat beyond p_n 5.8 (approx.) above which the slope of the curve is found to diminish appreciably probably because NH_4OH is driven off from the solution as NH_3 by bubbling of hydrogen gas, before it could react with the acid.

Titration curves as evident from the figure, never shoot up sharply in any region but lie flat with a relatively steep slope in a certain region indicative of an inflexion. The inflexion, occurring in each case between p_n 5 and 8, is nowhere very steep. The curves have all a comparatively flat initial portion followed by inflexions and final flattening at higher p_n values. The slow rise of the curve beyond the steeper inflexion indicates a continued interaction with the base even in this region. This portion occurs in almost all cases between p_n 10 and 11 excepting with NH_4OH , as already mentioned.

The titration curves with the different bases are not coincident. The curve for Ba(OH)_2 shows a longer flat portion in the initial stages of titration indicative of a relatively high buffering in this region. The titration curve for NH_4OH shows a steeper rise almost from the beginning. The initial buffering of the Ba(OH)_2 curve may be either due to the relative insolubility of the barium salt of the nucleic acid or to the higher coagulating power of the Ba-ion for this solution. Further, it may be mentioned that the courses of the titration curves are not such as to warrant the polybasicity of the acid from a casual inspection. This evidently suggests that either the acid is monobasic or, if polybasic, its dissociation constants are so close to one another as not to exhibit separate inflexions in the titration curves, *i.e.*, the inflexions overlap and present the characteristics of one continuous inflexion (Stuedel, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1921, 18, 119; Simms, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 1239, 1251).

To clarify this point it was thought desirable to analyse the titration curves further by drawing their buffer capacity curves (Van Slyke, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, 22, 525) by plotting db/dp_n against mean base, presented for one typical base in Fig. 3A. The buffer capacity curves are evidently complex and the existence of more than one minimum

is not clearly discernible. It was therefore necessary to try other methods for deciding this point unequivocally. The acid was therefore titrated by diluted bases very carefully (instead of using approximately ten times stronger bases). The two titration curves presented in Fig. 3B for NaOH and Ba(OH)₂ bring out clearly the existence of two in-

FIG. 3A

FIG. 3B

flexion points in the whole run of the curve up to p_n 10. All the other bases were similarly tried and in each case two inflexion points were visually noticeable. Titration curves of NaOH and Ba(OH)₂ have only been presented here and the rest not shown for economy of space. A summary of the analysis of these curves is presented in Table I below.

TABLE I

Base.	First inflexion		Second inflexion	
	p_n .	M.e. base per 100 g. acid.	p_n .	M.e. base per 100 g. acid.
NH ₄ OH	4.90	150	7.00	310
NaOH	4.75	165	7.10	325
KOH	4.60	168	7.00	360
Ca(OH) ₂	4.50	172	7.10	382
Ba(OH) ₂	4.30	182	7.10	390

It is evident from the above table that the p_n of the first inflexion with all the bases lies in the neighbourhood of 4.5 to 4.9, with about 165 m.e. of base per 100 g. of the acid. The concentration of the solution was 2 g. per litre and hence the actual amount of base required for this inflexion amounted to $2 \times 165 / 100 \times 10^{-3} = 3.3 \times 10^{-3}$ equivalents. The initial p_n of the acid solution was 2.95, whence $a_n = 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$. Hence the base required at the first inflexion is greater than that required to neutralise free acidity (hydrogen-ion activity).

The base required for the second inflexion point, which is the sharper of the two, gives the total acidity per 100 g. of the nucleic acid, since no further inflexion point

could be detected beyond this point up to p_H 10. Obviously the total acidity is not exactly a fixed quantity with the different bases studied but shows a slight variation in the order : $Ba(OH)_2 > Ca(OH)_2 > KOH > NaOH > NH_4OH$. Total acidity at a definite p_H also runs in the same order. The difference observed with different bases is, however, not very marked.

Calculating from the total acidity observed with NaOH viz., 325 m.e. per 100 g. of the acid, the equivalent weight of the acid roughly comes out to 308. Assuming the acid to be tetrabasic (cf. Steudel, *loc. cit.*) its molecular weight amounts to 1232. This compares favourably with the value of 1287 calculated from the simplest structural formula on the assumption of the tetranucleotidic composition of the acid.

Potentiometric titration curves thus show two dissociation constants and present the character of a weak acid. The ratio of free acidity per 100 g. of the acid, calculated from hydrogen-ion activity of the solution (viz., 1.2×10^{-3}), to the total acidity calculated for the same amount of the acid is 0.143 i.e., 14.3% only. Such low values can be expected of weak acids alone. The p_H of the second inflexion lies at about 7.1, a fact which is characteristic of strong acids alone. Such conflicting features cannot, however, be expected of acids in true solutions.*

(ii) *Conductometric Titration.*—Conductometric titrations were carried out with three different bases: KOH, $Ca(OH)_2$ and $Ba(OH)_2$. The results are graphically represented in Fig. 4. The curve for KOH shows two inflexions, one (A) corresponding to about 175 m.e. of base per 100 g. of the acid which tallies excellently with the first inflexion of the potentiometric titration curve. The second inflexion (B) occurs at about 370 m.e. of base which is also almost equal to the total acidity for 100 g. of the acid obtained potentiometrically. The course of the curve beyond second inflexion simulates strongly the alkali line. Between these two inflexions the specific conductance of the sol rises with addition of base to a value much above that for the original sol, and the curve thus resembles that of a weak acid.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

* Reference may be made in this connection to the extensive work on the potentiometric titration of different colloidal acids carried out by Prof. J. N. Mukherjee and co-workers published in this journal and also in *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*

Titration curves with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ present a complex character. First inflexion points (α and α') for these bases exhibit slight difference from each other and they are both higher than that for KOH. The curves for $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ are W-shaped. The final inflexion points (δ and δ') are far removed from those obtained by potentiometric titration with these bases. From the shape of the curves the relative order of total acidity appears to be the same as observed from potentiometric study viz., $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{KOH}$.

The peculiar shapes of the conductometric titration curves with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ are, however, difficult of explanation at the present stage. Further work appears to be necessary to get an insight into the mechanism going on in the system during its interaction with these bases. It is quite likely that the divalent cations, Ba^{++} and Ca^{++} , besides neutralising the acid, have in addition a precipitating effect either due to the formation of insoluble salts or by coagulation on the colloidal micelles of the nucleic acid anions. This point will form the subject matter of a future communication.

Interaction with Acid

A preliminary investigation was carried out by titrating a nucleic acid solution with HCl in the same way as in the case of the bases mentioned above. The hydrochloric acid solution used was approximately 10 times as strong as the nucleic acid solution in order to avoid any dilution effect when HCl was mixed with nucleic acid solution. Results have been graphically presented in Fig. 5.

For comparison, a study of the interaction of water with hydrochloric acid solution and of phosphoric acid with hydrochloric acid solution was also conducted in the same manner as with the nucleic acid solution. Results are shown graphically in the same figure. The phosphoric acid solution used was of the same p_K as the nucleic acid solution.

It will be evident from the figure that the curve for the nucleic acid occupies an intermediate position between those for water and phosphoric acid solutions. Nucleic acid solution has a greater buffering action compared to phosphoric acid since the p_K for equal additions of HCl is much higher with nucleic acid than with the latter.

It is well known that acidic properties of nucleic acids owe their origin to the existence of ionisable phosphoric acid groups present in the molecule. Hence a close similarity was expected in the interaction of nucleic and phosphoric acids with HCl. Although a broad similarity does actually exist, the difference at the same time is quite marked.

Levene ("Nucleic Acids", 1931, p. 284), however, concludes from the structure proposed by him that the phosphoric acid groups in the nucleic acid have only one ionisable hydrogen atom left for ionisation excepting one group which possesses two such atoms. Hence, the phosphoric acid groups should exhibit the primary dissociation mainly excepting one group which should show a secondary dissociation as well. In the phosphoric acid itself all the three different types of dissociation are probable and possibly they do exist. In the light of these observations it is quite rational to expect some difference between the two acids although both of them contain phosphoric acid groups responsible for its electrolytic ionisation. But whether this is quite sufficient to explain the observed facts awaits further investigation.

C O N C L U S I O N S

1. Potentiometric titrations of yeast nucleic acid were carried out with five different bases viz., NH_4OH , NaOH , KOH , $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$. Titration curves do not show very sharp inflexions characteristic of strong or moderately strong acids.
2. Further analysis of these curves brings out only two definite inflexions, the first one being slightly greater than that corresponding to the neutralisation of the free acidity. The p_a 's of the two inflexions are more or less the same for the different bases, the first one showing a greater variation (from 4.9 to 4.3) while the second one being more steady at 7.0 to 7.1, as the interacting base is changed.
3. The nucleic acid has no definite total acidity which has been observed to vary with the nature of the base used for interaction. The differences are, however, small and run in the order: $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{KOH} > \text{NaOH} > \text{NH}_4\text{OH}$.
4. Conductometric titrations with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and KOH also exhibit similar behaviour. KOH shows two inflexions and they fairly correspond with those of the potentiometric titration within limits of experimental accuracy. The titration curves for $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ present peculiar shapes. Total acidities show the same order of variation as in potentiometric titration with which they roughly agree.
5. Nucleic acid interacts with HCl in the same way as water and phosphoric acid. The difference is more quantitative than qualitative in nature.

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